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Domestic Credit to Private Sector

Between 2013 and 2021 it grew by an average of 6.22% for the countries considered

The World Bank calculates domestic credit to the private sector as a percentage of gross domestic product Domestic credit to the private sector refers to financial resources provided to the private sector by financial firms, for example through loans, non-equity purchases and credit commercial. For some countries domestic credit to the private sector also includes credit to public enterprises. Financial corporations include monetary authorities and depository banks, as well as other financial corporations for which data is available. Examples of other finance companies are leasing companies, money lenders, insurance companies, pension funds and exchange companies. The data analyzed refer to the period between 2013 and 2021. Only countries with a complete historical series in the analyzed period were taken into consideration.

Ranking of countries by the value of domestic credit to the private sector as a percentage of gross domestic product in 2021. Croatia ranks first in the value of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP with a value of 399.30%, followed by Hong Kong with a value of 259.47%, Macao SAR with a value of 236.46%, United States with a value of 216.33%, and Japan with a value of 194.09%. In the middle of the table are Kenya with a value of 31.12%, followed by Guyana with a value of 30.82%, Senegal with a value of 29.85%, Burkina Faso with 29.42%, Belarus with an amount of 29.17%. The Congo Dem. Rep. closes the ranking with a value of 7.22%, followed by Zimbabwe with a value of 6.99%, Sudan with an amount of 6.62%, and Sierra Leone with an amount of 0 .01%. In 2021, on average, the value of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP was 61% for the countries considered.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in the value of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2021. Uzbekistan ranks first in the value of the percentage change in domestic credit as a percentage of GDP with a value equal to 281.87 %, followed by Macao with 278.08%, Cambodia with a value of 219.65%, Qatar with 208.34%, South Sudan with a value of 142.55. In the middle of the table are Togo with an amount of -3.83%, followed by Iceland with an amount of -4.66%, Pakistan with an amount of -4.74%, Benin with an amount of - 5.27%, from ST Vincent and the Grenadines with a value of -5.35%. The ranking is closed by Greece with a value of -51.86%, followed by Zimbabwe with a value of -62.69%, Cyprus with a value of -63.31%, Ukraine with a value of -66.68%, Ireland with a value of 73.31%. Between 2013 and 2021, the value of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP on average for the countries considered rose from 57.6% to a value of 61.27%, i.e. a change of +6.22%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization achieved using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Elbow's method is a graphical method to identify the optimal number of clusters in connection with the k-Means algorithm. Four different clusters are then identified.

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- Cluster 1: Ukraine, Belize, Latvia, Peru, Philippines, Paraguay, Kosovo, Serbia, Bangladesh, Lithuania, Jamaica, West Bank and Gaza, Indonesia, Brunei Darussalam, Hungary, Albania, Trinidad and Tobago, Nicaragua, Ecuador, Tonga, Guyana, Maldives, Botswana, Guatemala, Mexico, Sierra Leone, Kenya, South Sudan, Solomon Islands, Congo Dem. Rep., Suriname, Moldavia, Uzbekistan, Romania, Malawi, Sudan, Zimbabwe, Togo, Iraq, Senegal, Chad, Guinea, Egypt, Haiti, Belarus, Dominican Republic, Niger, Guinea Bissau, Equatorial Guinea, Central African Republic, Nigeria, Uruguay, Tajikistan, Madagascar, Algeria, Rep. Congo, Mali, East Timor, Uganda, Kyrgyzstan, Libya, Papua New Guinea, Ghana, Comoros, Pakistan, Zambia, Burundi, Djibouti, Ivory Coast, Rwanda, Benin, Micronesia, Swaziland, Lesotho;
- Cluster 2: Thailand, China, Japan, Denmark, Norway, South Korea, United Kingdom, Australia, United States, Sweden, Hong Kong, Cyprus, Malaysia, South Africa, Chile, Spain, Macao, Portugal, Netherlands;
- Cluster 3: Croatia;
- Cluster 4: Germany, Morocco, Barbados, Jordan, Samoa, Italy, Turkey, Austria, Israel, Malta, Estonia, Belgium, Brazil, Vanuatu, Nepal, St. Lucia, Fiji, Honduras, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Iceland, Qatar, Cambodia, Cabo Verde, El Salvador, Slovakia, Costa Rica, Grenada, Kuwait, Oman, Georgia, Vietnam, Bulgaria, Luxembourg, Russia, Mongolia, Bhutan, St Kittis and Nevis, Armenia, Poland, Montenegro, Antigua and Barbuda, India, North Macedonia, Czechia, France, Greece, Ireland, Dominican Republic, Slovenia, Colombia, St. Vincent and the Grenadines.

From the point of view of the median we can see that the following ordering of the clusters is $C3=399,305 > C2=139,305 > C4=67,2 > C1=26,11$. The clustering model is in any case strongly misaligned due to the presence of a cluster which is the C3 made up of a single country, namely Croatia. In reality, Croatia is an outlier in this data set as it has very high levels of domestic credit to the private sector as a percentage of GDP. That is, the credit that Croatian banks and financial organizations grant is about 4 times higher than Croatia's GDP. This is obviously an oversized value that highlights the presence of significant international investments or for reasons related to tourism or real estate speculation. In fact, Croatia has a significant endowment of cities and real estate structures on the Mediterranean which could give rise to financial-real estate speculation. In second place for the value of the median we find cluster 2 made up of a large number of countries among which China, Japan, the countries of Northern Europe and Scandinavia stand out, and also some countries with medium-low per capita income such as the South Africa and Chile. In the countries of this cluster, domestic loans cover about 139% of GDP as a median value. Then there are the countries of Cluster 4 which finance with domestic credit about 64% of GDP as a median value. In cluster 4 it is possible to identify some countries with medium-high per capita income such as Germany, Italy, Australia, Israel, Iceland, Luxembourg, Poland, France, Ireland. However, in this cluster there are also a set of growing countries such as Russia, India, Brazil, and other countries of central and southern America, of the Arabian Peninsula. The countries of cluster 1 close the ranking, i.e. a set of countries with low-average per capita incomes that are very varied from a strictly geographical point of view. In summary, except for the case of Croatia, it appears that the investment endowment of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP is typical of countries with medium-high per capita incomes or high GDP growth rates.

Conclusions. Between 2013 and 2021, the average value of domestic credit towards the private economy as a percentage of GDP grew for the countries considered by an amount of 6.2%. We can note that, except for Croatia, the countries that have high levels of GDP growth also have a high level

of domestic financing. Conversely, countries with low economic growth rates tend to have low levels of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP. The data therefore seem to suggest the importance of banking, financial and insurance institutions, and organizations in promoting economic growth at the country level. It follows that the well-known "*finance-growth nexus*" discussed by economists Luigi Zingales and Raghuram Rajan turns out to be an essential determinant of economic growth and development. To promote economic development at the country level, it is also necessary to create financial, banking and organizational institutions and organizations capable of offering credit to the private sector.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University "Giuseppe Degennaro" and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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